

EXPLORING THE COMPETENCIES OF RURAL ENTREPRENEURS: PERSPECTIVES FROM A DEVELOPING COUNTRY CONTEXT

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Abstract

Purpose – This paper aims to investigate current business models and present a conceptual framework based on the results of market research and will present the partial results obtained within the SusRural project that is underway at the Politehnica University of Timisoara and to create a theoretical framework for improving the entrepreneurial skills of individuals.

Methodology/approach – It uses qualitative assessment based on market research. This model captures the most important trends in economic development in rural areas, needs for the training of entrepreneurs, innovation or technology and other peculiarities.

Findings – Entrepreneurial competences must be developed in competence centers for fields of activity and development environments. The research presents the characteristics of the entrepreneurs who established their business during the project.

Research limitations/implications – The entrepreneurial environment is dynamic and encountered both in urban and rural areas. The development of entrepreneurship in rural areas needs to be supported at national and international level.

Practical implications – Social entrepreneurship is a challenge for entrepreneurs because it is not aimed at registering profit through the work they carry out.

Originality/value – The development of entrepreneurship in the rural area is an activity with a major impact in the economy of the future and with many challenges.

Key words: Rural entrepreneurship, business model, entrepreneurial skill.

Introduction

Entrepreneurship is the best way to innovate, create and make an idea become reality and generate profit. Business development in rural areas is a national concern (Cioca et al., 2019). Business models contribute to the development of rural areas. These models generate economic and social value and develop the creativity of the area. Social enterprises and insertion social enterprises respect the principles of the social economy and serve the interest of the community. The principles of the social economy are part of the general objectives of sustainable development (Ambrus et al., 2018). Social entrepreneurship as a peculiarity of entrepreneurship is gaining a lot of interest in the business area. Emphasizing the involvement of the entrepreneur in the social environment and investing profit in the issues of society are dimensions of entrepreneurship in the social economy.

The 21st century brings new challenges, urban population growth, climate change and increasingly limited natural resources are becoming topics of major interest worldwide (Francesco Orsini, 2021). Another concept of the social economy refers to urban agriculture. Urban agriculture, which means growing food in cities, promotes a healthy lifestyle and the involvement of local communities. Identifying the main models of networking and advice to form a significant critical mass of successful entrepreneurs contributing to sustainable rural economic development.

The purpose of this paper is to present the results of a market research that was carried out in 2021 to identify the entrepreneurial training of the target group. The target group consists of 75 potential entrepreneurs. The sample of this research was formed by the target group of the SusRural project

implemented at the Politehnica University of Timisoara. The general objective of this project is to establish 21 social enterprises or social insertion enterprises. The entrepreneurs are from the western part of Romania. These companies will operate for 18 months, to which 6 months of sustainability are added. Each company has at least 5 employees and received a subsidy of 100,000 euros (SusRural website, 2022).

The first part presents the specialized literature in the entrepreneurial field. Then the results of the market research are presented. The next chapter presents different business models in research area. The work ends with the presentation of a model of entrepreneurship in rural areas. The last section presents the conclusions, limitations, and future research directions.

Literature Review

The present world is going through a strong process of urban concentration which causes major changes in production processes, supply chains, adaptation to the new requirements of life. Urban agriculture has been closely linked to the existence of cities (Lawson, L. 2016). Within urban agriculture, the idea of local entrepreneurs who can have production activities in the peri-urban area appears. Urban agriculture is a solution that can be applied individually or organizationally (Harada et al., 2020; Hume et al., 2021).

Although there are currently few studies and research in the field, most agree that this form of agriculture is a modern one and that can co-exist with the urban social environment (Hou, H. 2019). Food and nutritional security, quick and easy access to organic food, short distances in the distribution chain are clear benefits of urban agriculture (Langemeyer, J. 2021).

The development of rural entrepreneurship represents a challenge and an opportunity to contribute to the development of the local economy and the strengthening of the community. As shown in the study (Langemeyer, J. 2021; Cioca et al., 2019), entrepreneurs from different social fields invest resources and complex skills to become competitive. Some costs are lower (for example space rent), but the challenge of the rural environment remains an important component.

The year 2019 introduces a new problem in the food safety equation, the COVID-19 pandemic. The impact that the pandemic has had on the way of supply is major. Strict containment measures to prevent the spread of the virus have prevented the movement of people and goods, affecting especially the supply chain of rural farmers' markets (Pulighe, G. 2020). The potential of urban gardens has been positively highlighted during the pandemic as a quick solution to the restrictive measures taken, but also to the cooperation between urban and rural areas in terms of technologies, capital, and talent (Inwood, S. 2017).

Methodology

The present research uses qualitative research and empirical experience to highlight the results obtained. The target group consists of 75 potential entrepreneurs. Of the 75 responses received, 63 were validated, the rest being incomplete or incorrectly transmitted. For data collection we used a questionnaire that so far has been completed by several 63 people (58.7% female, 41.3 male, Figure 1), 51% from urban areas and 49% from rural areas, Figure 2.

With a higher education level of 48% and a master's degree of 28%, Figure 3. This research is ongoing process, and this paper presents the intermediate results obtained from study.

Age of the sample on which the questionnaire was applied is presented below, Figure 4.

Figure 1. The gender of the respondents

Figure 2. Respondent's living environment

Figure 3. The level of education

Figure 4. Age of the sample on which the questionnaire was applied

Results and discussion

The group on which the initial analysis was carried out consists of 25 people who currently have a business, 28 do not have any business, 6 have an NGO and 2 people do not answer or do not know, Figure 5.

Figure 5. The status of business in present

The entrepreneurial experience highlighted that 63% of the participants in the study have entrepreneurial experience and 37% have none, Figure 6.

Figure 6. Entrepreneurial experience

Currently, 43 people have a concrete business idea, 19 have several ideas but have not decided and one person has no idea, Figure 7.

Figure 7. The entrepreneurial status of the respondents

In the study it resulted the amount they would need to start a business according to the study participants is 57% for > 150000 euro and 30% for 10000 euro – 30000 euro, Figure 8. The need for financing a small business is not very high and solutions can be found through European and national programs.

Figure 8. Amount range they would need to start a business

Regarding theoretical knowledge, 73% did not participate in an entrepreneurial training program, respectively 27% were involved in a learning process, Figure 9.

Figure 9. Have you participated in entrepreneurial training courses so far?

From this group of the respondents 68% have experience in developing a business plan, respectively 32% have never developed a business plan, Figure 10.

Figure 10. Have you ever developed a business plan?

The entrepreneurial courses followed by the respondents contribute to the development of entrepreneurial skills. When asked about the extent to which these courses helped the respondents, it can be observed that 31 of the respondents say that they helped them a lot, 25 it helped them a lot and 7 it helped them a little, Figure 11.

Figure 11. The entrepreneurial courses contribute to the development of respondents' competencies

The interest for a certain economic field showed the majority orientation towards production activities (17 people), agriculture (14 people), cultural activities (8 people), tourism and IT (5 people), Figure 12.

Figure 12. Economic area of interest resulting from the questionnaire

The barriers encountered by the respondents in the way of developing a business are presented in Figure 13. It can be observed that most respondents did not have financial resources (28 respondents) and 14 of them currently have another business in which they are not majority shareholders.

Figure 13. The barriers in the development of a personal business

The needs of entrepreneurs in developing their own businesses are meetings with other entrepreneurs to exchange ideas, smart contracts, workshops for the development of business communication skills, networking, strategic management, personal branding, mentoring/counseling, personal branding, and participation in trade fairs or events in the industry where you will develop your business. The distribution of answers to these needs is presented in Figure 14. It can be seen that the meetings with other entrepreneurs are the most appreciated by the respondents (37 respondents).

Figure 14. The needs of entrepreneurs in the development of their own businesses

Discussion

The general objective of the SusRural project is to strengthen economic and social cohesion in the West region to combat poverty and socio-economic integration of people belonging to vulnerable groups. Social entrepreneurship is a challenge for entrepreneurs because it is not aimed at registering profit through the work they carry out.

These learning methods can constitute an analysis of a distinct work and that manages to capture the characteristics and particularities of rural entrepreneurship and in the development of a successful learning model. Making incubators and simulation games for entrepreneurship activities can help through concrete examples for participants to discover what mistakes can be made and how they learn from them (Ciolac et. al, 2022).

The factors contributing to the adoption of urban agriculture have positive and negative results. These connotations affect mental and physical perception.

The entrepreneurial process involves creativity, risk-taking and innovation (Hu, R., Wang, 2018). This study highlights the factors that need to be addressed to increase food safety, and health at work.

These methods of education can constitute an analysis of a distinct work that succeeds and captures the characteristics and particularities of entrepreneurship and the development of entrepreneurship a successful model.

A studied model presents the basic levels that must be considered for the development of a theoretical framework. This model includes characteristics of the entrepreneur (temperament, attitude, knowledge) and capacities for rural development (Zamani, N., and Mohammadi, M., 2018; Hou et al., 2018). The studied model (D'Ostuni, F., and D'Ostuni, M., 2021) presents the main elements of a development model: the characteristics of the entrepreneur, the location of the business, external features, internal features, and innovation.

Based on the models studied and the market research undertaken, the important levels of an entrepreneurship model in the rural environment can be outlined: the characteristics of the entrepreneur (the most important being passion, motivation, communication, and financial resources), innovation, the entrepreneurial knowledge of the individual and the attitude towards of the social dimension. Model of entrepreneurship in rural areas in our vision is presented in Figure 15.

Figure 15. Model of entrepreneurship in rural areas

Conclusions

Supporting the development of businesses in the rural environment contributes to the economic growth of the respective environment, to the improvement of the standard of living and to the integration of the community in the dynamic business environment. The obtained results emphasize that the respondents are interested in the development of some social enterprises in the rural environment. At the same time, it was observed that many of the respondents had previous entrepreneurial experiences or had tangential ones.

The development of entrepreneurship in rural areas is an activity with a major impact in the economy of the future and with many challenges. Identify key learning and counselling models to form a significant critical mass of successful entrepreneurs contributing to sustainable rural economic development.

The limitations of this research refer to the domicile of the respondents. The domicile of the respondents should be in the Western Region of Romania. As future research, we will aim to expand the research at the national and international level.

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